

Influence of the fiber curvature on the mechanical properties of long fiber reinforced composites

Celine Lauff, Matti Schneider, Thomas Böhlke | 04.08.2025, ICCM 2025

Motivation

(Andrä et al., 2014)

Information on real
microstructures, e.g., from μ CT-scans

Microstructure
generation

Synthetic microstructures

State of the art - selected literature

Modeling the fibers as straight cylinders:

- Sequential insertion algorithms:
 - Random sequential addition (RSA) algorithm (Feder, 1980; Widom, 1966)
 - Extensions of the RSA algorithm (Chen et al., 2019; Lauff et al., 2023; Tian et al., 2015, 2021)
- Collective rearrangement algorithms:
 - Mechanical contraction method (MCM) (Williams et al., 2003)
 - Sequential addition and migration (SAM) algorithm (Mehta et al., 2022, 2024; Schneider, 2017)

⚡ limited to short fiber-reinforced microstructures

State of the art - selected literature

Modeling the fibers with curvature:

- RSA and compression in thickness direction
(Fliegener et al., 2014)
 - + Enables industrial fiber packings
 - Computationally complex finite element analysis is necessary
 - Fused sequential addition and migration algorithm
(Lauff et al., 2025a, 2024)
 - + Computationally efficient
 - + Enables industrial fiber packings
- ⚡ no fiber curvature control

Overview

- 1 **Description of discontinuous long fiber-reinforced microstructures**
- 2 fSAM algorithm for long and curved fibers
- 3 Extension of the fSAM algorithm for curvature control
- 4 Computational investigations

Description of discontinuous long fiber-reinforced microstructures

Curved fiber

- Fiber described by curve:

$$\mathbf{c}_i : [0, L_i] \longrightarrow Q,$$

$$Q = [0, Q_1] \times [0, Q_2] \times [0, Q_3]$$

- Parametrization by arc length:

$$\|\mathbf{c}'_i(s)\| = 1, \quad s \in [0, L_i]$$

description of a curved fiber

(Schneider, 2022)

Description of discontinuous long fiber-reinforced microstructures

Fiber orientation tensors

(Advani et al., 1987)

$$\mathbb{A}_{\langle k \rangle} = \frac{1}{L} \sum_{i=1}^N \int_0^{L_i} \mathbf{c}'_i(s)^{\otimes k} ds$$
$$\mathbf{A} \equiv \mathbb{A}_{\langle 2 \rangle}, \quad \mathbb{A} \equiv \mathbb{A}_{\langle 4 \rangle}, \quad L = \sum_{i=1}^N L_i$$

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Fiber volume fraction

$\phi = 5\%$

$\phi = 20\%$

$$\phi = \frac{V_f}{V}$$

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aspect ratio:

$$r_a = \frac{L_{\text{mean}}}{D}$$

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Size of the unit cell

$$V = Q_1 Q_2 Q_3$$

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fSAM algorithm for long and curved fibers

Discretization for long and curved fibers

- Parametrization:

starting point	\mathbf{x}^0	} $a = 1, \dots, n$
directions	\mathbf{p}^a	
lengths	$\ell = \frac{L}{n}$	

fSAM algorithm for long and curved fibers

Discretization for long and curved fibers

- Parametrization:

starting point \mathbf{x}^0
 directions \mathbf{p}^a
 lengths $\ell = \frac{L}{n}$

} $a = 1, \dots, n$

- Coordinate vector:

$$\mathbf{q} = \left[(\hat{\mathbf{x}}^0)^T \quad (\mathbf{p}^1)^T \quad \dots \quad (\mathbf{p}^n)^T \right]^T$$

with normalization:

$$\hat{\mathbf{x}}^0 = \hat{\mathbf{Q}}^{-1} \mathbf{x}^0 \quad \text{with} \quad \hat{\mathbf{Q}} = \text{diag}(Q_1, Q_2, Q_3)$$

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Configuration space

$$\mathcal{R} = \left\{ \mathbf{q} \in \mathbb{R}^{3(n+1)} \mid \Phi_1(\mathbf{q}) = \mathbf{0} \right\},$$

$$\Phi_1(\mathbf{q}) \triangleq [\Phi_1^1(\mathbf{q}) \quad \dots \quad \Phi_1^n(\mathbf{q})]^T \quad \text{with} \quad \Phi_1^a(\mathbf{q}) = \frac{1}{2} (\|\mathbf{p}^a\|^2 - 1), \quad a = 1, \dots, n$$

fSAM algorithm for long and curved fibers

Minimization problem

$$F(\mathbf{q}_1, \dots, \mathbf{q}_n) \longrightarrow \min_{\mathbf{q}_1, \dots, \mathbf{q}_n} \mathbf{q}_i \in \mathcal{R}_i$$

$$F(\mathbf{q}_1, \dots, \mathbf{q}_n) \hat{=} \underbrace{\frac{1}{2} \sum_{i,j=1}^N \sum_{a=1}^{n_i} \sum_{b=1}^{n_j} (\delta_{ij}^{ab})^2}_{\text{non-overlap condition and fiber orientation tensor}} + \frac{w_A}{8} \|\mathbb{A} - \mathbb{A}^r\|^2$$

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$$+ \underbrace{\frac{w_{\rho}}{2} \sum_{i=1}^N \sum_{a=1}^{n_i-1} (\rho_i^a)^2}_{\text{angle constraint}}$$

$$\rho_i^a = \langle \cos \alpha_i - \mathbf{p}_i^{a+1} \cdot \mathbf{p}_i^a \rangle_+$$

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Extension of the fSAM algorithm for curvature control

Quantifying the fiber curvature of a single fiber

- Fiber orientation of a single fiber:

$$\mathbf{A}_f = \frac{1}{L} \int_0^L \mathbf{c}'(s) \otimes \mathbf{c}'(s) ds$$

description of a curved fiber

(Schneider, 2022)

Extension of the fSAM algorithm for curvature control

Quantifying the fiber curvature of a single fiber

- Fiber orientation of a single fiber:

$$\mathbf{A}_f = \frac{1}{L} \int_0^L \mathbf{c}'(s) \otimes \mathbf{c}'(s) ds$$

- Deviation from straight curve (DSC):

$$K_f = \text{tr} \left(\frac{1}{L} \int_0^L (\mathbf{A}_f - \mathbf{c}'(s) \otimes \mathbf{c}'(s))^{\otimes 2} ds \right)$$

$$= 1 - \|\mathbf{A}_f\|^2$$

Extension of the fSAM algorithm for curvature control

Quantifying the fiber curvature of a single fiber

(Lauff et al., 2025b)

Extension of the fSAM algorithm for curvature control

Volume-averaged DSC:

$$\bar{K} = \frac{1}{L_{\text{total}}} \sum_{i=1}^N L_i K_f^i,$$

Objective function with extended curvature control

$$F(\mathbf{q}_1, \dots, \mathbf{q}_n) \longrightarrow \min_{\mathbf{q}_1, \dots, \mathbf{q}_n} \quad \mathbf{q}_i \in \mathcal{R}_i$$

$$F(\mathbf{q}_1, \dots, \mathbf{q}_n) \hat{=} \underbrace{\frac{1}{2} \sum_{i,j=1}^N \sum_{n_i}^{a=1} \sum_{n_j}^{b=1} (\delta_{ij}^{ab})^2 + \frac{w_A}{8} \|\mathbb{A} - \mathbb{A}^r\|^2}_{\text{non-overlap condition and fiber orientation tensor}} + \underbrace{\frac{w_\rho}{2} \sum_{i=1}^N \sum_{a=1}^{n_i-1} (\rho_i^a)^2}_{\text{angle constraint}} + \underbrace{\frac{w_K}{8} n_s (\bar{K} - \bar{K}^r)^2}_{\text{DSC}}$$

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Computational investigations

Algorithmic Choices

- Relative error of the fiber orientation state $< 10^{-4}$
- Relative error of the DSC state $< 10^{-3}$
- Minimum distance: $2.0\mu m$
- Maximum segment length: $\bar{\ell} = 25\mu m$
- Maximum bending angle: $\bar{\alpha} = 30^\circ$
- Closure approximation: Exact closure (Montgomery-Smith et al., 2011a,b)

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Material

- $Q_i = 400\mu m$
- $D = 10\mu m$
- $L = 1000\mu m$
- $\mathbf{A} \hat{=} \text{diag}(0.75, 0.15, 0.1)$

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Homogenization with an FFT-Solver (Schneider, 2021; Zeman et al., 2010)

- Approximation of the **orthotropic** engineering constants
- Polypropylene matrix: $E = 1.25 \text{ GPa}$, $\nu = 0.35$ (DOW[®] Chemical Company, 2003)
- E-glass fibers: $E = 72.0 \text{ GPa}$, $\nu = 0.22$ (PPG Fiber Glass, 2013)

Computational investigations

Generated microstructures with varying fiber curvature

Computational investigations

Generated microstructures with varying fiber curvature

(a) $\bar{K} = 0.06$

(b) $\bar{K} = 0.15$

(c) $\bar{K} = 0.25$

(Lauff et al., 2025b)

Computational investigations

Runtime for the microstructure generation

(Lauff et al., 2025b)

Computational investigations

Effect of the fiber curvature on the mechanical properties

(Lauff et al., 2025b)

Computational investigations

Effect of the fiber curvature on the mechanical properties

Computational investigations

Effect of the fiber curvature on the mechanical properties

Computational investigations

Study on the maximum segment length

(Lauff et al., 2025b)

Computational investigations

Study on the maximum segment length

Conclusion

- fSAM algorithm with **fiber curvature control**
 - Novel measure to quantify the fiber curvature: **deviation from straight curve** (DSC)
 - Extension of the objective function

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- fSAM algorithm with **fiber curvature control**
 - Novel measure to quantify the fiber curvature: **deviation from straight curve (DSC)**
 - Extension of the objective function
- Computational investigations
 - fSAM algorithm is capable of realizing a **wide spectrum of curvatures**
 - Significant **Young's moduli reduction** for increased fiber curvature

Thank you for your attention!

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fSAM algorithm for long and curved fibers

Solving the minimization problem

$$F(\mathbf{q}) \longrightarrow \min_{\mathbf{q} \in \mathcal{R}}$$

- Gradient descent approach
 - ⚡ Standard gradient descent approach: \mathbf{q} may leave its configuration space

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Moving along the geodesics

- Geodesic (Petersen, 2016):
 - Shortest path between two points on a manifold
 - Minimizing the energy functional

fSAM algorithm for long and curved fibers

Exponential mapping

- For the geodesically complete Riemannian manifold $(\mathcal{R}, \mathbf{G})$:

- Input:

- Tangent vector $\mathbf{v} \in T_{\mathbf{q}}\mathcal{R}$
- Point on the manifold $\mathbf{q} \in \mathcal{R}$

- Output:

$$\exp_{\mathbf{q}}(\mathbf{v}) = \mathbf{q}_v(1)$$

- $\mathbf{q}_v : [0, 1] \rightarrow \mathcal{R}$: unique geodesic with $\mathbf{q}_v(0) = \mathbf{q}$ and $\dot{\mathbf{q}}_v(0) = \mathbf{v}$

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Adapted gradient descent approach

$$\mathbf{q}^{k+1} = \exp_{\mathbf{q}^k} \left(-\tau_k \nabla_{\mathbf{q}} F(\mathbf{q}^k) \right), \quad k = 0, 1, \dots,$$

